

RF UPSET SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF CMOS AND LOW POWER
SCHOTTKY D-TYPE, FLIP-FLOPS*

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ABSTRACT

EMC assurance technologies for high speed, high density integrated circuits are currently of interest [1-4]. Integrated circuit chips for the military arena must be electronically robust. They must be reliable and operate compatibly without functional upset in severe electromagnetic environments.

This paper describes measurements of RF upset levels on two D-Type flip-flops, CD4013B and 54ALS74A, functionally identical and from different technologies, CMOS and low power Schottky. CW EMI from 1 MHz to 200 MHz was coupled into the clock, data, and Vcc ports of each device type while test vectors were used to verify normal operation and subsequent upsets.

The data suggest some useful trends to compare upset threshold levels in a HF-VHF environment for a widely used digital circuit, fabricated from current and competitive technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Electronic systems designed for today's military and commercial arenas are prodigious users of complex, semiconductor integrated circuits (ICs). Design strategies for fabricating advanced circuit devices that are both electromagnetically compatible and cost effective are often in conflict. In most systems designed for the military arena, the constituent chips either singly, in arrays, or in hybrid modules must all function acceptably and reliably. They must collectively perform a system function for a specified duration in an often unspecified, but always stressful, RF electromagnetic environment.

In some surprisingly common scenarios [5,6], sources in these environments can produce interfering RF power levels of 40-50 dBm at susceptible system ports at frequencies ranging from 10 MHz to 100 GHz. In other related studies [7], both experimental and analytical data suggest that if these power levels at the system ports are not sufficiently attenuated, they can cause upset in digital devices with pin susceptibilities from +20 dBm to -40 dBm.

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BACKGROUND

Previous studies [8-10] also indicate that the primary mechanism for RF induced upset in semiconductor devices is interference signal rectification. If sufficient RF spectral power levels are coupled into the victim chip and can propagate to susceptible PN junction(s), the RF may be detected as video and/or baseband signals and DC offset. The resulting in-band spectral components may be further processed and subsequently masquerade as "desired", although aliased, functional signals.

It appears from the available data that below the f_c (i.e., the cutoff frequency at which the transistor current gain is 0 dB) of a victim circuit device, an in-band interference RF signal may be "normally" processed as the desired signal. This effect may then account for timing related upsets, logic time shifts, and false state transitions.

Above the device f_c , the out-of-band rectification (nonlinear) processes seem to predominate: RF detection may produce DC offset voltages (and currents) in the victim devices' transfer functions. The resulting bias shifts often account for further upset and timing errors elsewhere on the chip beyond the immediate junctions affected. RF signals that remain undetected can also propagate to other susceptible devices on the same chip or (couple) to other chips in the same module or on the same board until detected or dissipated.

The analytical and empirical upset data suggest that (a) rectification efficiency decreases with increasing frequency by as much as 40 dB/decade; (b) upset susceptibility increases with increasing f_c , i.e., higher likelihood of EMI in high speed digital and microwave linear circuits; (c) upset susceptibility increases with decreasing feature size; and (d) upset susceptibility increases with increasing chip density of nonlinear junctions.

PROBLEM

Upset error and nonlinear distortion responses that are induced by EMI spectral energy coupled into chip (and system) architectures are generally unknown design parametrics. Wideband, or even narrowband, RF susceptibility data for most chips are not normally provided as environmental stress factors to relate degraded device parameters with subsequent circuit upset. They are not CAD options: they're missing from the design (rule) menus.

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TEST DEVICES

Without RF susceptibility databases and attendant (EMI) mitigation buffer design parameters for intrachip electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) assurance, the existing CAD rules are incomplete. As a corollary, EMC design technology for circuits and systems in electromagnetically stressful environments will remain an active and important issue.

TEST CONFIGURATION

In order to provide appropriate temporal and spectral databases for RF EMI assessments and mitigation designs, an integrated circuit test facility has been assembled. Figure 1 shows the RF susceptibility test configuration. First, it allows for functional testing without EMI to verify and characterize the devices' normal operating baseline (NOB) performance. The digital analysis system functionally exercises and monitors the response of the device under test (DUT). Next, RF interference test waveforms are synthesized, monitored, and additively combined with the normal operating functional signals. The resulting composite signal is then conductively coupled into the package pin(s) of interest on the DUT. Between the combiner and the DUT pin interface, there are provisions for measuring the upset voltages at the test pins.

In these tests the DUT environment is of special interest. The test device is installed on a carrier fixture card that is mounted in the vacuum chamber of a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). With test devices suitably prepared, i.e., delidding and depassivating, for example, this test setup can help to pinpoint, track, and measure at micron-levels, the possible RF rectification (offsets), propagation, intertrace coupling, and other abnormal nodal responses due to the injected EMI signals.

Figure 1. RF test configuration including SEM interface.

The device types chosen for this study are the CD4013B and the 54ALS74A, D-Type flip-flops. The former device is fabricated (processed) using Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) technology and the latter with bipolar, Advanced Low Power Schottky (ALS) technology. The CMOS device uses a 10 micron geometry and the ALS device, a 3 micron geometry. The RF upset susceptibilities of these device types should differ due to the different device fabrication technologies and input structures used.

The CMOS device uses complementary n-channel and p-channel metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistors (MOSFETs) as the active circuit devices while the low power Schottky device uses Schottky clamped bipolar transistors. The input of the CMOS device has an electrostatic discharge (ESD) protection network followed by the gates of the MOSFETs.

The ESD protection network in the CMOS input is composed of a diffused resistor that has reverse biased, discrete diodes tied to ground at both ends. Because of the construction of this diffused resistor, it also acts as a distributed diode to Vcc with the junction capacitance distributed along its length. By comparison, the input of the low power Schottky device is a reverse biased Schottky diode tied to ground and followed by the base of a Schottky clamped transistor.

As noted previously, the transistor feature size in the advanced low power Schottky device is smaller than that in the CMOS device. Thus, the f_t should be higher for the Schottky device than the CMOS device. This is evident in the specified maximum clock frequency for each device: 50 MHz for the low power Schottky device versus 3.5 MHz for the CMOS device.

The functional diagrams for both device types are shown in figure 2: both devices are logically identical except for the set and reset functions. The clear and preset of the 54ALS74 (Schottky) are equivalent to the reset and set of the CD4013 (CMOS), respectively.

The functional exercise of the devices' logic during RF upset testing uses the same test vectors for both device types. Comparison of the RF threshold levels required for respective upset provides insight to differences between device technologies and input structures.

Figure 2. Functional diagrams for test devices.

SESSION 4B

TEST DESCRIPTION

Figure 3 illustrates the test methodology. In this approach, the DUT is first operated in its intended mode without EMI to measure the actual NOBs and to validate them against the vendor supplied data sheets. At this point, upset criteria for a given test device had been defined that window the "unacceptable" deviations in the device's normal operating parameters due to the RF interference.

The RF interference test waveforms are then applied and increased in some suitable temporal or spectral dimension (for example, power/voltage level, frequency, or time delay) until an upset in the test device occurs. The threshold levels required to cause upset are recorded and printed out. The DUTs are again exercised without the EMI to reconfirm that the normal operating baselines are still intact.

During NOB and RF interference testing, the data, clock, set (preset), and reset (clear) pins are all exercised by the functional test program. Both flip-flops in each DUT are exercised even though only one flip-flop is injected with RF interference. The Q and the Q(not) outputs of both flip-flops are monitored for their response. The flip-flop is clocked at a frequency of 1.25 MHz and the data pin is toggled at 625 kHz. The DUT response is sampled at a 5 MHz rate. Since the DUT output is toggling at a much slower rate, timing errors are detected.

While the functional test program is executing, the DUT response is stored in the digital analysis system. The test program is repeated until memory space is filled, there are seventy-five cycles of the functional test program for each run.

Figure 3. Functional upset flow diagram.

Prior to RF interference injection, the response of the DUT to the functional test program is stored as the NOB. After acquiring the NOB, RF interference is injected into the DUT at a particular port of entry. The level of RF interference is increased until a deviation from the NOB is detected. A deviation occurs when either or both Q and Q(not) outputs go to an unintended NOB state. A single deviation detected in each of two consecutive runs with functional recovery verified both times after removal of RF interference is considered upset. The RF voltage and frequency amplitude required for upset are recorded.

The RF interference is discrete CW at 1.2, 5, 10, 50, 100, and 200 MHz. The ports of entry are clock, data and Vcc. Due to limited capabilities of the combiner output current drive, upset at 100 and 200 MHz was not always possible without risk of permanent damage.

The complex input impedance of the port of entry was measured at each test frequency and the RF power required for upset was calculated using equation (1).

$$P_{ave} = (1/8)V_{pp}^2 \{R / (R^2 + X^2)\} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{ave} is average RF power, V_{pp} is peak to peak RF voltage, R is the real part of the input impedance and X is the imaginary part of the input impedance.

TEST RESULTS

RF Susceptibility

Two units of each device type were tested for RF upset susceptibility. Table 1 lists the RF power (dBm) required for upset at each frequency tested. The asterisk denotes frequencies at which no upset could be induced.

F(MHz)	Vcc pin upset power in dBm			
	ALS 74		CD4013	
	S/N 1	S/N 4	S/N 1	S/N 2
1.2	6	4	-31	-30
5	5	5	5	2
10	6	5	6	5
50	6	5	14	14
100	9	9	22	24
200	6	*	*	*

F(MHz)	Data pin upset power in dBm			
	ALS 74		CD4013	
	S/N 1	S/N 4	S/N 1	S/N 2
1.2	-26	-27	-35	-33
5	-20	-20	-28	-25
10	-22	-17	-19	-18
50	-14	-15	-5	-4
100	-10	-7	0	5
200	-10	*	*	*

F(MHz)	Clock pin upset power in dBm			
	ALS74		CD4013	
	S/N 1	S/N 4	S/N 1	S/N 2
1.2	-29	-29	-34	-36
5	-29	-29	-23	-25
10	-28	-28	-18	-15
50	-20	-21	-2	-1
100	-14	-15	-1	6
200	-10	-12	*	*

Table 1. Summary of RF power upset levels for each device at each frequency tested.

SESSION 4B

The current drive capability of the combiner was limited at higher frequencies due to limited bandwidth of the op-amp used in the combiner. Figure 4 is a plot of RF upset power versus frequency for the 54ALS74 (S/N 1). Figure 5 is a similar graph for the CD4013 (S/N 1). Each curve identifies the specific port of RF entry. Figures 6, 7 and 8 compare RF upset threshold levels at Vcc, clock and data pins, respectively, for the two types of device technologies tested: shown are data for S/N 1 devices.

Figure 4. RF upset power versus frequency for the Schottky 54ALS74, S/N 1.

Figure 5. RF upset power versus frequency for the CMOS CD4013, S/N 1.

Figure 6. RF upset power versus frequency comparison for the CMOS circuit versus the Schottky circuit with RF entry into the Vcc pin.

Figure 7. RF upset power versus frequency comparison for the CMOS circuit versus the Schottky circuit with RF entry into the clock pin.

Upset Description

During all tests where RF interference was injected into the data or clock input of a flip-flop, only that flip-flop was driven to upset. On the other hand, when RF interference was injected into the Vcc pin, upset usually occurred in both flip-flops.

The initial upset event for the CD4013 was the Q output staying high for 200 ns too long before going to the intended low level. This event occurred when set was changing from high to low and reset was toggling from low to high. The Q(not) output remained at the NOB during initial upset and then deviated when the RF power level was increased above the level for the initial upset. This type of upset occurred with RF injection at all three ports of entry.

Figure 8. RF upset power versus frequency comparison for the CMOS circuit versus the Schottky circuit with RF entry into the data pin.

With RF interference injected into Vcc on the 54ALS74, the device upset event occurred when Q(not) went low one clock cycle before an intended high to low transition. With increased levels of RF interference power, the Q output also would begin to deviate from the NOB.

Both the Q and the Q(not) output deviate from the NOB at the same RF power level with RF interference injected into the 54ALS74 clock input. Both outputs, Q and Q(not), changed logic state one clock cycle before the intended logic state change. Both outputs also deviated from the NOB at the same power level with RF interference injected into the data pin. The Q output stayed at a low logic level (Q(not) high) until preset and clear were brought from the high state to a low state.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Analysis of the data displayed in figures 4 - 8 provides the following:

Figure 4

- 1) The Vcc port of the Schottky device has a relatively constant RF susceptibility level of 6 dBm from 1 MHz to 200 MHz.
- 2) Both data and clock ports indicate decreasing RF susceptibility in the range from 1 MHz to 200 MHz, with approximate (average) roll-offs of 3 dB/decade from 1 MHz to 10 MHz, and 12 dB/decade from 10 MHz to 200 MHz.

Figure 5

- 1) The Vcc port of the CMOS device exhibits decreasing RF susceptibility in the range from 1 MHz to 100 MHz and roll-offs of about 60 dB/decade from 1 MHz to 5 MHz and 15 dB/decade from 5 MHz to 100 MHz.
- 2) Both data and clock ports also indicate decreasing RF susceptibility in the range from 1 MHz to 100 MHz with an average roll-off of about 18 dB/decade.

Figure 6

This shows the Vcc port susceptibility levels for the two measured technologies in contrast. The Schottky device has a constant upset level of 6 dBm over the band while the CMOS device has a decreasing RF susceptibility with at least two distinct roll-offs as discussed previously for figure 5.

Figure 7

This clearly shows the RF hardness of the CMOS clock port over the Schottky clock port in the range of 2 MHz to 100 MHz where the advantage can be as much as 18 dB. Below 2 MHz, the relative advantages seem to reverse; i.e. the Schottky device may be "RF harder" than the CMOS device, but there is insufficient data to be certain.

Figure 8

This shows the decreasing RF susceptibilities of both data ports from 1 MHz to 200 MHz for the two technology samples measured. Except now, we note a possible "transition" band from 5 MHz to 10 MHz wherein the relative advantages again seem to reverse.

UPSET FACTORS

An exact determination of all the factors contributing to the differences in RF susceptibility is beyond the scope of this paper. Four factors, however, are suggested; namely differences in: f_t , device processing, geometry dimensions, and input circuitry.

Though f_t was not explicitly measured, the relative difference between the two device types can be inferred from the maximum clock frequency specification. For operation at five volts the maximum clock frequency specification for the CMOS device is 3.5 MHz versus 50 MHz for the low power Schottky device.

As discussed earlier, the fabrication process and geometry dimensions also differ. The CD4013 is fabricated using 10 micron CMOS technology and the 54ALS74 is fabricated using 3 micron ALS technology.

Also as discussed earlier, the input circuits for the two device types differ. The input circuitry for the clock and data pins is different because of the ESD protect networks used. The CMOS device uses a diffused resistor with discrete diodes while the low power Schottky device uses a Schottky diode tied to ground.

CONCLUSION

- 1) Both the CMOS and the Schottky devices show decreasing RF susceptibility with increasing frequencies from 1 to 200 MHz.
- 2) The differences in the susceptibility levels measured for the two technologies are apparent in the data and clock ports' upset levels. The CMOS device roll-off is almost 18 dB/decade as compared to about 12 dB/decade for the Schottky device.
- 3) The differences in Vcc ports' susceptibilities are also apparent. The CMOS device's upset levels decrease steeply with increasing frequency at approximate roll-offs of 60 dB/decade up to 5 MHz and 15 dB/decade from 5 to 100 MHz. Over the same bands, the Schottky device susceptibility at the Vcc port remains strikingly constant at a 6 dBm upset level.

SESSION 4B

4) Finally, the measurements on the clock and data ports seem to suggest that: (a) the CMOS device is "RF harder" than the Schottky device by 3 to 18 dB at least above the 5 to 10 MHz range and out to 100 MHz; (b) below that range, the Schottky device may be "RF harder" by 3 to 6 dB, but there are not enough measurements data to confirm this performance below 5 MHz.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. J. Whalen, "Demodulation RFI Statistics for A 3-Stage OPAMP LED Circuit," in Proceedings IEEE International Conference on EMC, Atlanta, GA, Aug. 1987.
- [2] J. G. Tront, "Predicting RFI Upset of MOSFET Digital ICs," IEEE Trans. on EMC, Vol. EMC-27, No. 2, May 1985.
- [3] D. J. Kenneally and G. O. Head, "EMI Noise Susceptibility of ESD Protect Buffers in Selected MOS Devices," in Proceedings IEEE International Conference on EMC, Wakefield, MA, August 1985.
- [4] J. N. Roach, "The Susceptibility of a 1K NMOS Memory to Conducted Electromagnetic Interference," in IEEE EMC Symposium Record, Boulder, CO, August 1981.
- [5] H. W. Denny, "Projected Trends in Electromagnetic Environment Interactions," in SOUTHCON 87 Professional Program Session Record, Atlanta, GA, March 1987.
- [6] H. W. Denny, J. K. Daher, J. P. Rohrbaugh, "Integrated Circuits Technology Assessment (ICTA) Project, Final Technical Report: Definition Phase," F41621-83-C-5015, AFEWC, San Antonio, TX, April 1984.
- [7] H. W. Denny, "Projected Susceptibilities of VHSIC/VLSIC Devices to the Year 2000 Electromagnetic Environment," in Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on EMC, San Diego, CA, September 1986.
- [8] R. E. Richardson, "Modeling of Low-Level Rectification RFI in Bipolar Circuitry," IEEE Trans. on EMC, Volume EMC-21, No. 4, November 1979.
- [9] R. E. Richardson, "Quiescent Operating Point Shift in Bipolar Transistors with AC Excitation," IEEE Journal of Solid State Circuits, Volume SC-14, No. 6, December 1979.
- [10] R. E. Richardson, "Microwave Rectification of RFI in Logic Circuitry," in NBS Conference on Microelectronic Electromagnetic Susceptibility, Gaithersburg, MD, March 1985.